

Cryptographic Services to Enforce Secure Messaging and Data Storage

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Abstract:- In secret key cryptography, a single key is used for both encryption and decryption. It achieves privacy and confidentiality. In this, sender sends the cipher text by encrypting the plain text with a secret key and receiver decrypts the cipher text by using same secret key to generate original plain text. The secret key must be shared between two authorized users secretly to apply at both the ends for encrypting and decrypting. Major challenge of secret key cryptography is the key sharing i.e., distribution of secret key to the sender and the receiver. This paper discusses the symmetric key cryptographic algorithms and evaluates step by step procedure of the algorithms with respect to the key bit size.

Keywords:- *Cryptography, Security, Symmetric Key, Cryptosystems, Plain Text, Cipher Text, Encryption, Decryption, Symmetric Algorithms,*

I. INTRODUCTION

In this digital technology world, the cyber threats plethora has been increasing day by day. Emerging internet use is proportionally decreasing the quality of the security. Thus the security experts must concentrate on the measures to reduce the risks in the cyberspace. As we know the cryptosystems are secured by its broad classification into two i.e., (i) symmetric key cryptography - shared key (single key) must be used for both encryption (process of transforming plain text to cipher text) and decryption (process of transforming cipher text to plain text), and (ii) asymmetric key cryptography - public and private key combinations are used for encryption and decryption i.e., public or private key is used at one end and vice versa at other end. But, despite of the advantages, there are many facts that the secret information is being revealed or copied directly to the opponent. Thus, this paper discusses the terminology of most prominently used secret key cryptographic algorithms with respect to their key size and implement in a better way to control the trust of clients. It also notifies how to use the key and challenges faced by sender and receiver.

II. CRYPTOGRAPHY IS EVERYWHERE

Almost all ancient civilizations knew cryptography as a special linguistic phenomenon, fixing on physical media the “secret languages” that existed in different social groups since time immemorial. These languages have an origin in magical ritual, but later they were understood as a tool for

social communication. In this regard, cryptography has two main application areas in the ancient history:

“magic” – to conceal a meaning of names, magic rituals, secret ritual knowledge and another taboo information, i.e. for secret communications with the supernatural (that was an integral part of the lives of all ancient civilizations);

“practical” – to protect military reports, personal correspondence, and perhaps trade secrets, i.e. for secret communication in human society.

The most important encryption principles – replacement and permutation of characters – were empirically discovered in the Ancient World. In the Ancient World, these principles exhausted the arsenal of cryptographic protection methods for written texts, and they were realized only for special, very simple cases. Evolution of the cryptographic methods was extremely slow because the existing methods were generally sufficient.

Along with cryptography, the ancient civilizations used various methods of physical protection of messages by encoding and steganography. That served different practical purposes such as concealing the fact of message’s existence or transfer, hiding the names of senders or recipients, accelerating copying text and reducing the amount of material to be carried or memorized, transmitting messages at a rate greater than a man’s speed, and raising the value of the text to the reader. These objectives were often seen as a priority compared to concealing the message’s meaning from unauthorized persons.

While studying cryptography in the Middle Ages and the early New Ages (XVI – XVII centuries) it is reasonable to stress the following:

1. The encryption methods have become more complex in the Middle Ages: polyalphabetic substitution has been invented. The systematic methods of cryptanalysis have appeared in the Arabian world for the first time;
2. Signatures and stamps ensured a document’s authenticity for the first time in Byzantium, along with encryption ensuring the confidentiality of documents;
3. Ciphers are still considered a linguistic phenomenon: single words, sentences, paragraphs, sections of the document are converted.

One of the techniques that can be used to indicate a close relationship between history and modernity of cryptography and to inspire students who are accustomed to think in terms of modern mathematics and formal logic is to mathematically analyze ancient ciphers (like shift, replacement, affine and permutation ciphers). However, the general cases of substitutions and (or) permutation were not

implemented in any classical ciphers and cryptographic devices, and the particular cases used essentially reduce the cipher strength. Nevertheless, a number of examples might illustrate the fact that the most secure classic ciphers such as the Vigenère cipher and “Latin squares” are widely regarded as almost unbreakable until the appearance of computers in the XX century.

Fig 1:Classical and provable Cryptology

III. CRYPTOGRAPHY AND ITS TYPES

Cryptology is the study of cryptography and cryptanalysis. The procedure of changing original form of data to meaningless code by using any algorithm at sender and from meaningless code to original form of data by using same algorithm at receiver is known as cryptography [1]. To secure information we must encode the form of data into unreadable meaningless code.

The act of obtaining the plaintext or key from the encoded text that is used to obtain plaintext information to pass on modified or fake messages in order to deceive the original intended recipient i.e., breaking the cipher text is referred to as cryptanalysis.

Breaking ciphers may be legal or illegal. This type of breaking the ciphers depends on the types of hackers i.e., either white hat hackers who are legal and certified hackers or black hat hackers who are illegal and bad at works. There are gray hat hackers also who will in the field of legally illegal or vice versa.

Fig 2: Cryptology Branches

A. Basic Cryptography

Fig 3: Basic Cryptography

Cryptography is of two types i.e., Symmetric cryptography and asymmetric cryptography. In Symmetric cryptography both sender and receiver will use same key called secret key which will be shared between sender and receiver for both encryption and decryption, whereas in asymmetric cryptography both sender and receiver will have their own set of public and private key combinations. Public

key will be shared to network but private key will be maintained confidentially at their end points. If the encryption is done at sender by receiver’s public key then it can be decrypted only by receiver’s private key and if the encryption is done at sender by sender’s private key then it can be decrypted by sender’s public key at receiver end.

B. Symmetric Cryptosystems

Fig 4: Symmetric Cryptography

C. Asymmetric Cryptosystems

Fig 5: Asymmetric Cryptography

IV. FUTURE SCOPE AND CONCLUSION

Cryptography concerns the invention of encryption algorithms and the invention of decrypting methods. One of the cryptography methods that can be said to be currently attracting is “quantum cryptography”. Quantum means the “minimum unit that can be measured”, and here it refers to a photon, i.e., a quantum of light. Photons vibrate as they move. Encrypted information can be received by measuring the angle of photon vibrations, and whenever a communication is intercepted by anyone other than the intended recipient, the angle changes, thereby ensuring that the interceptions will be detected. The reason encryptions by quantum cryptography are considered impossible to decrypt, whereas encryptions in the past were considered “undecryptable within a reasonable amount of time”, is that the change in angle of the vibrations makes it possible to detect interceptions.

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